

Generative Variational Autoencoder model of musical scales based on Slonimsky’s thesaurus

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Abstract

This paper explores the application of artificial intelligence in symbolic music generation, focusing on the use of a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) trained on the Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns by Nicolas Slonimsky. We consider two main tasks: generating novel musical scales and interpolating between known and generated scales. The analysis includes an evaluation of generated scales using metrics such as novelty, symmetry, and coverage, as well as assessments of interpolation quality through structural similarity and local binary pattern analysis. The results indicate that the model is capable of producing musically coherent and structurally diverse scales, demonstrating its potential as a tool for assisting composers in exploring new melodic frameworks. While the approach successfully captures key characteristics of Slonimsky’s scales, certain limitations remain, including dataset constraints and the need for more quantitative evaluation methods. These findings contribute to ongoing research on AI-assisted music composition, suggesting directions for future improvements, such as expanding datasets, refining evaluation metrics, and exploring the model’s potential for transfer learning in other musical contexts.

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in deep learning have enabled groundbreaking progress in domains such as image synthesis, natural language processing, and audio generation. Within the realm of music, these technologies have shown promise for tasks ranging from transcription and accompaniment to novel composition. This paper investigates whether deep generative models, specifically a Variational Autoencoder trained on Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns*, can generate novel and musically coherent scales that extend beyond the compositional structures present in the dataset.

To achieve this, we designed a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) and trained it on musical scales extracted from Nicolas Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns* (Slonimsky, 1947)².

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²Github Repository: <https://github.com/benjasaldias/Symbolic-Music-Generation/>

This thesaurus, comprising over 1,000 scales, offers a rich and structured resource for experimenting with musical creativity. The reasoning behind choosing a VAE model over others is due to its particular advantages for this work:

- **Structured and continuous latent space:** Enables smooth interpolations between training and generated scales, revealing how the model organizes the musical structures within the latent space. This is particularly valuable for exploring transitions and variations among related musical patterns. Unlike a VQ-VAE (van den Oord et al., 2018), which uses discrete latent representations and limits interpolation, a standard VAE’s latent space allows more nuanced transformations and gradual morphing between musical structures.
- **Proven effectiveness in music generation:** VAEs have demonstrated strong performances in music generation tasks. For example, PocketVAE successfully generates expressive drum patterns (Lee et al., 2021), and EmoMusicTV incorporates emotional conditioning into symbolic music generation (Ji and Yang, 2024).
- **Efficient and lightweight:** Unlike more recent models such as GANs (Goodfellow et al., 2014) or Transformers, VAEs are less computationally expensive and can be trained effectively on relatively small datasets. Their simpler architecture enables faster training cycles and easier tuning.
- **Aligns with the nature of the dataset:** Slonimsky’s Thesaurus systematically explores scales through transformations and symmetry. A VAE naturally aligns with this approach, as its latent space captures structural relationships, enabling interpolation, variation, and the generation of novel yet coherent scales.

The objective of this study is twofold: (1) to evaluate the ability of a deep generative model to create new scales that extend beyond its training data, and (2) to assess its capability to interpolate smoothly between scales, generating intermediate results with musical coherence. The overarching goal is to develop AI tools that augment the creative process for musicians, enabling them to explore new ideas and compositions.

2 Background

Nicolas Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns*, first published in 1947, is an important work in the field of music theory and composition. This exhaustive collection comprises a vast array of scales, melodic patterns, and interval sequences meticulously organized and classified. Designed as a resource for composers, musicians, and theorists, the *Thesaurus* provides an unprecedented exploration of pitch organization, serving as a foundational tool for innovative approaches to melody and harmony.

Nicolas Slonimsky (1894–1995), a Russian-American conductor, composer, and theorist, developed the *Thesaurus* during a time of intense experimentation in Western music. The early 20th century saw the decline of strict tonal traditions and the rise of alternative frameworks such as atonality, twelve-tone serialism, and modal improvisation. Slonimsky sought to contribute to this era of innovation by creating a systematic methodology for exploring scales and patterns beyond traditional tonal systems.

The *Thesaurus* has been embraced by a wide range of musicians, from avant-garde composers to jazz improvisers and even rock guitarists. Notably, it profoundly influenced John Coltrane, whose advanced harmonic progressions and modal structures bear the unmistakable marks of Slonimsky’s methodologies (Bair, 2003).

The *Thesaurus* organizes its content using mathematical principles applied to musical intervals. Scales and patterns are derived through the following methods:

- **Symmetry:** Most scales in the *Thesaurus* exhibit symmetrical intervallic structures, providing balance and aesthetic appeal.
- **Subdivision of Octaves:** Scales are constructed by dividing one or more octaves into equal or irregular parts, such as using minor thirds or whole-tone steps. Each chapter in the *Thesaurus* covers a whole subdivision of a certain amount of octaves, for example, the Quinquetone (five tone) Progression divides 5 scales into six equal parts.

- **Chromatic Permutations:** Melodic patterns are generated by rearranging pitches chromatically or diatonically, producing permutations that maintain coherence while introducing novelty.

Slonimsky’s work continues to hold relevance across musical genres due to its adaptability and intellectual depth. It bridges the gap between mathematical abstraction and artistic expression, enabling musicians to innovate while staying grounded in theoretical rigor. The enduring legacy of his thesaurus lies in its ability to inspire musicians to view scales not as static entities but as dynamic frameworks for exploration and creativity.

3 Related work

Symbolic music generation using variational autoencoders (VAEs) has emerged as a promising approach in the field of AI-driven music composition, leveraging the ability of VAEs to capture complex musical structures and styles. The use of MIDI-based generative neural networks with VAEs has shown potential in creating music that maintains structural integrity and authenticity, although challenges remain in achieving optimal convergence in the latent space, particularly when dealing with diverse training data and the complexities of representing data in multiple dimensions (Rosalina and Sahuri, 2024). The Multi-view MidiVAE model addresses some of these challenges by employing a two-dimensional representation to capture note relationships and reduce feature sequence length, thereby improving the modeling of long multi-track symbolic music (Lin et al., 2024). Additionally, the integration of style embeddings in VAEs allows for enhanced control over the generated music, enabling the production of genre-specific compositions that capture stylistic nuances (Mosin and Belov, 2024). The concept of sub-task decomposition, which separates high-level structural planning from content creation, has been proposed to better model musical structure, although capturing the nuanced development of themes remains difficult (Bhandari and Colton, 2024). Furthermore, the use of fine-grained discriminators to decouple melody and rhythm has been shown to improve the quality of generated music by allowing more precise adjustments to mimic human-composed music (Zhang et al., 2024). The development of models like MeloTrans, which incorporate human compositional habits and motif development rules, highlights the importance of merging human insights with neural network capabilities to enhance musicality and diversity in generated compositions (Wang et al., 2024). Despite these advancements, the scarcity of symbolic training data poses a challenge, prompting innovative approaches such as using pre-trained Music Information Retrieval (MIR) models to extract symbolic events from audio data (Chen et al., 2024). Overall, the integration of VAEs in symbolic music generation continues to evolve, with ongoing research focusing on improving structural coherence, stylistic control, and the ability to generate long-term compositions.

4 Methodology

4.1 Dataset Description

The dataset was derived from a subset of Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns*, which contains over 1,000 scales and melodic patterns, meticulously annotated to capture their structural and tonal properties. Each scale was encoded as a symbolic matrix representation, suitable for input into a neural network (see Subsections 4.2 and 4.3 for further details on the encoding format and data preparation). The choice of this dataset was motivated by its diversity and historical significance. Its exhaustive collection of scales provides an ideal testbed for exploring the generative capacity of AI models in music.

Currently, our model is trained with 227 scales of Slonimsky’s thesaurus, which are all the scales in the thesaurus that have 37 notes each. Setting a specific and constant length for all scales in the dataset reduces the chances of getting problems with noise in generated data, helping us understand the capabilities of the model for music generation.

The thesaurus navigates the musical octaves through thorough exploration of permutations of notes for each progression (or subdivision of octaves). Each chapter contains the scales that follow a certain structure of “principal tones”, which are the notes pertaining to the chapter’s progression. Variations of each progression are made via adding up to four notes within each principal tone interval. Notes can be added by three insertional techniques:

- Interpolation: The added note is within the interval of principal tones surrounding it.
- Infrapolation: The added note is lower than the interval of principal tones surrounding it.
- Ultrapolation: The added note is higher than the interval of principal tones surrounding it.

Figure 1: Scale construction methods for the *Thesaurus*.

Note that these scale construction methods are specific to Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus* and refer to how he derived each progression. They are conceptually unrelated to the interpolation techniques applied in our model’s latent space or during data augmentation.

4.2 Model Architecture

We selected a variational autoencoder (VAE) due to its proven effectiveness in generative tasks (Kingma and Welling, 2013). A VAE comprises two primary components, as shown in figure 2:

- An encoder that maps input data into a lower-dimensional latent space z , capturing its essential features.
- A decoder that reconstructs data samples from this latent representation.

Both encoder and decoder are CNN-based, enabling the model to effectively capture local patterns in the input matrices.

Figure 2: VAE architecture diagram.

New data is generated by sampling random or selected vectors from the latent space with the trained decoder.

4.3 Pre-processing

As our model receives tensors as input, we settled our data’s format to be similar to a piano roll, which represents music in a matrix form. As each of our dataset’s scales has 37 notes, scales will be

transformed into a 37x63 matrix, with 63 being the amount of notes needed to represent the scales we include in our dataset. The dataset was augmented by transposing each training scale (twice) by a random amount of semitones between -3 and 3, resulting in 681 scales.

4.4 Training Procedure

The model was trained using an input dimension of 2331 (37x63), one hidden convolutional layer of size 256, and a 12-dimensional latent space, resulting in $1,412,031^3$ trainable weights for the $37 \times 63 \times 681 = 1,587,411$ notes of the training set. Training spanned 1500 epochs, during which both reconstruction loss (measuring fidelity to the input) and KL divergence (promoting smoothness in the latent space) were minimized.

The model was trained in four different ways, each time increasing the amount of scales considered for training, to get an overview of how the complexity and size of the dataset affect the musical coherence and novelty of the generated data.

The scale groups were selected based on the thesaurus' chapters and subsections, as each new section implies a different approach to scale construction, which, in theory, will make our model learn new and more complex features.

The model was implemented using the PyTorch framework. Training was carried out using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $3e-5$ and a batch size of 16. ReLU was used as the activation function throughout the encoder and decoder networks. Training was performed on a single GPU and took approximately 10 minutes per model variant, allowing constant retraining.

The training sets were the following:

1. 9 scales (augmented to 27): Corresponds to the first subsection of the first chapter; Tritone Progressions: Interpolation of two notes.
2. 84 scales (augmented to 252): All valid Tritone Progressions (of length of 37 notes).
3. 200 scales (augmented to 600): Adds all valid Ditone Progressions to the previous set.
4. 227 scales (augmented to 681): Adds all valid Quadritone Progressions to the previous set.

Note that the hyperparameters for each training case were optimized individually. The resulting metrics were gathered in **Table 1**.

4.5 Generation Metrics

To assess the model's performance, we implemented metrics such as:

- Novelty: A measure of the dissimilarity between generated and training data. Its result is binary, returning 0 for a scale belonging to the dataset, and 1 for a scale that is unknown or new.

$$\text{Novelty} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if generated} \in \text{dataset,} \\ 1 & \text{if generated} \notin \text{dataset.} \end{cases}$$

- Sparseness: Quantifies the amount of played notes in a scale. It ranges from 0 to 1, where higher values mean more notes were played, while a lower value means the opposite.

$$\text{Sparseness} = \frac{\text{number of active notes}}{37 \times 63}$$

Given that the Thesaurus has a sparseness score of 0.0159—where each row contains exactly one active note—we can interpret sparseness as an indicator of note distribution across time. A higher sparseness score suggests multiple active notes per row, while a lower score implies that some rows may have no notes at all. This metric is useful for verifying that the number of notes per scale remains consistent, allowing us to rule out changes in sparseness as the cause of variation in other metrics.

³ $(2331 * 256) + (256 * 12 * 2) + (12 * 256 + 256) + (256 * 2331 + 2331) = 1, 205, 275$

- Coverage: Measures the percentage of different notes played throughout the scale. It ranges from 0 to 1, where higher values mean a wider diversity of notes were played, and a lower one means fewer notes were played or more notes were repeated. As enharmonic equivalents were taken as different notes, this may lower the coverage score value.

$$\text{Coverage} = \frac{\text{columns with at least one active note}}{\text{total number of columns}}$$

- Symmetry: Indicates how symmetric a generated scale is. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 represents perfect symmetry and 0 total asymmetry. In this context, symmetry refers to the presence of a central pivot note (typically at the midpoint of the scale), such that for every note at position i from the start, there exists a corresponding note at position $n - i - 1$ (its mirror position from the end) with the same pitch-class interval relative to the center. A perfectly symmetric scale has identical intervals when read forwards and backwards from this central note.

$$\text{Symmetry} = \frac{1}{18} \sum_1^{18} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } M[18 - i] = M[18 + i], \\ 0 & \text{if } M[18 - i] \neq M[18 + i]. \end{cases}$$

4.6 Interpolation Methods

We have implemented two different ways of interpolating over the model’s latent space:

- Two-Scale Interpolation: smooth transition between two chosen (or randomly sampled) scales. The amount of steps will be 10 or lower, eliminating possible repeated scales.
- Four-Scale Interpolation: returns a 5x5 grid of scales, having the four input ones on each corner, traveling the latent space from one point to another.

In both features, we have implemented the option of choosing between LERP⁴ and SLERP⁵ interpolations (Jafari and Molaei, 2014), as shown in figures 3 and 4. Linear interpolation (LERP) computes a straight-line path between two points, interpolating each component independently, while spherical linear interpolation (SLERP) calculates the shortest path on the surface of a sphere between two points, maintaining constant angular velocity. Both methods are used to interpolate between two points, but LERP is suitable for linear paths and can result in non-uniform motion, whereas SLERP is ideal for interpolating rotations and ensures uniform motion along a curved path. For the case of two-scale interpolations, as figure 3 shows, the inputs to the encoder can be either scales contained in the thesaurus or randomly generated scales that are run through the encoder to find their respective locations in the latent space (z_1, z_2). Then, interpolation vectors $s_1, s_2 \dots s_n$ are interpolated with either LERP or SLERP. These vectors are passed through the decoder to generate the output interpolated scales.

A four-scale interpolation repeats the two-scale interpolation process several times to form a grid, as shown in figure 4. Any corner can be generated or known from the dataset.

More on how to use the model’s features is presented in our anonymous GitHub repository.

4.7 Interpolation Metrics

The quality of our VAE’s interpolations was measured with these two metrics:

1. Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM): Measures the similarity between two images by considering structure, luminance, and contrast (Wang et al., 2004). In our case, SSIM is applied to scales represented in matrix or piano roll formats, with a default patch size of 7x7. SSIM values range from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates identical images, and lower values indicate increasing structural differences. It is computed using the following expression:

$$\text{SSIM}(A, B) = \frac{(2\mu_A\mu_B + C_1)(2\sigma_{AB} + C_2)}{(\mu_A^2 + \mu_B^2 + C_1)(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2 + C_2)}$$

⁴A function that uses linear interpolation to return a value between two given values.

⁵An interpolation technique that travels along the surface of a hypersphere between two points (e.g., quaternions or normalized vectors), often used to maintain constant angular velocity.

Figure 3: Diagram of our model’s two-scale interpolation process.

- μ_A is the mean of the local patches in image A. Same for B.
 - σ_A^2 is the variance of the local patches in image A. Same for B.
 - σ_{AB} is the covariance between the local patches of images A and B.
 - C_1 and C_2 are small constants to avoid division by zero.
2. LBP Euclidean Distance (LBPED): The LBP measure is a texture descriptor that identifies local patterns in data, encoding patterns based on relationships between neighboring points/pixels (Sedaghatjoo et al., 2024). The LBP function receives a matrix, the radius to search for local patterns, and amount of points/neighbors to consider in them. LBPED averages the euclidean distances between the LBP (Sedaghatjoo et al., 2024) values of two images. A higher LBPED means higher structural differences between both images, and a lower one means the opposite; still, note that an LBPED equal to 0.0 does not mean totally equal matrices, instead it indicates they possess the exact same local patterns.

$$LBP_X = LBP(X, \text{Radius}=6, \text{Points}=6)$$

$$LBPED(A, B) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (LBP_A - LBP_B)^2}$$

Theoretically, the maximum LBP Euclidean Distance between two of our scales is 31376 (varies depending on *radius* and *points* variables). Such a high value is not realistically achievable, and even less so between pieces of data that are already within the same structural parameters. For that motive we give as reference the highest LBPED between two of our dataset’s scales, which is 230.52.

Figure 4: Diagram of our model’s four-scale interpolation process.

By calculating the SSIM and LBPED value of each step of an interpolation, we can analyze the smoothness in the transition scales. In the case of four-scale interpolation, we evaluate the same metrics between each scale and its neighboring scales in the generated grid.

5 Results

As has been mentioned previously, this research is centered around two main ideas: generating new, musically coherent/interesting scales as well as interpolating on generated and/or known data, navigating the trained latent space. Thus, our results consist of running a sufficient amount of generations and interpolations, which shall be evaluated with the chosen metrics, able to measure correctly the efficiency and precision of our model’s capabilities.

5.1 Generated Scales

Table 1: Metrics evaluation over the whole dataset and 1000 pieces of randomly generated data from each training case.

Scales	Sparseness	Coverage	Symmetry	Novelty
Thesaurus	0.0159	0.3016	1.0000	-
27	0.0159	0.2988	0.9994	0.5250
252	0.0159	0.2912	0.9991	0.7425
600	0.0159	0.2765	0.9991	0.9487
681	0.0159	0.2790	0.9990	0.9537

As table 1 shows, our model exhibits capabilities of learning the necessary patterns in the dataset, with a constant major increase in the novelty score as the training set becomes more complex. Almost every piece of generated data is perfectly symmetrical, which is one of the main important qualities of a scale that the model must learn correctly.

Table 2: Training hyperparameters for each training case.

Scales	H DIM	Z DIM	Batch Size	Epochs	Loss
27	64	8	4	1000	81
252	160	12	6	1000	124
600	256	12	12	1000	286
681	256	12	32	1200	239

While sparseness does not vary from the thesaurus’ value, meaning the amount of notes per score is the same; the coverage metric has a slight decrease, which is linked to the increasing complexity of the latent space. This means that, as the data becomes more diverse, the latent space has more spaces where the distribution is more ambiguous; hence, the scales associated with those vectors have less variation in notes. Fortunately, this has had no visible impact on the generation nor interpolation of scales.

These metrics demonstrate that our model’s output is not merely ”refined noise” formatted as sheet music. Notably, among all generated scales—93.6% of which are novel—almost all exhibit perfect symmetry, maintaining the same note count as those in the thesaurus (as indicated by the Sparseness metric). Additionally, the model achieves a coverage reduction of only 3%, further supporting the structural coherence of the generated scales.

Most of the generated scales we tested by ear were musically coherent and displayed innovative patterns that extended beyond the original dataset. The main creative aspect of our generation process is that it diverges from the insertional techniques established by Slonimsky, varying both the type of techniques applied to each principal tone interval. This variability led to the creation of an entirely new category of scales, which can be further explored within the latent space, as demonstrated in the following examples.

5.1.1 Generation examples

The following figure presents a generated scale that has qualities reminiscent of Egyptian and Middle Eastern music, such as the maqamat melodic modes, being particularly similar to the Hijaz Maqam, due to its augmented second interval, followed by a minor third, as figure 5 displays.

Figure 5: Generation example: Resembling the Hijaz Maqam mode.

This sample illustrates the point made previously by breaking away from the rule of repeatedly using the same insertional techniques for each section of the scale.

The next example in figure 6 presents a scale that contains all 13 notes present in the musical octave; it doesn’t closely resemble any widely recognized scale. It still adheres to the fundamental structure of Slonimsky’s scales, while creatively diverging from the established rules for insertional techniques, freely exploring variations and new possibilities.

Figure 6: Generation example: Symmetrical chromatic pattern.

5.2 Two-Scale Interpolation Experiments

Interpolation between scales in the latent space yielded smooth transitions. Intermediate scales maintained musical plausibility, often combining features of the two endpoints in unexpected and creative ways. These interpolations highlight the potential of the model to aid composers in exploring variations and combinations of musical ideas, providing access to unique melodic patterns.

After performing 500 different interpolations, we calculated the average SSIM and LBPED values for each interpolation step, as well as for the transition between the first and last steps. This analysis helps us assess the structural similarity between the interpolated scales and compare it to the average metrics for each step. A higher average SSIM and lower LBPED per step indicate a smooth transition through the latent space from one scale to another. The results of the two-scale interpolations are presented in tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Metrics evaluation over 500 two-scale interpolations using the SLERP method.

SLERP	per step	start-finish
SSIM	0.8960	0.5497
LBPED	5.8853	12.8746

Table 4: Metrics evaluation over 500 two-scale interpolations using the LERP method.

LERP	per step	start-finish
SSIM	0.8911	0.5367
LBPED	6.005	13.1523

As shown in tables 3 and 4, both interpolation types had very similar results. A high SSIM and low LBPED per step (compared to the start-finish values) indicate that the transition scales for an interpolation from our model have a very smooth structural shift from one scale to another.

5.2.1 Two-Scale Interpolation Examples

We will now show the different ways our model’s interpolation can be used and the purposes it can fulfill. This first example interpolates between two known scales (that belong to the training scales). The first one is number 243 from Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus*, a ditone progression with infrapolation of two notes, while number 8 is a tritone progression with interpolation of two notes, as shown in figure 7.

Knowing the structural difference between these two, the transition from one to the other is very smooth, as well as musically coherent. Interpolating between known scales is a straightforward way for a composer to experiment with musical ideas of their liking, and get to a melodic pattern that suits their work. A clear display of creativity is shown in the middle steps, as the *Thesaurus* limits its scales to a specific type of the three insertional techniques, whilst steps 1 through 3 show combinations of them that still remain symmetrical and structured by their principal tones.

The next example shows an interpolation between a known scale and a randomly generated one. This is another important feature of our model, as it covers the situation where a composer wants to see variations of a particular known melody or scale, as shown in figure 8.

The 252nd thesaurus scale is a ditone progression with infrapolation of two notes, while the last step (random generation) has a less strict and mathematical approach, not being able to fit into any of the subsections of Slonimsky’s text. This scale includes the principal tones of a ditone progression, but the insertional techniques do not follow a specific pattern or structure. Still, the scale adheres to the other learned principles of scale creation, having its own principal tones, an ascending and descending order, and symmetry.

The difference and subtlety of the resulting variations will vary based on the LBPED and SSIM distance between the interpolated data. This way, we can grant our future users the ability to explore freely our diverse scale repertoire.

Lastly, the upcoming example interpolates over two randomly generated scales, as shown in figure 9. In contrast with the other examples, we offer this feature as an extension of generating and

Thesaurus scale 243

Thesaurus scale 8

Figure 7: Two-scale interpolation example: between scales 243 and 8 from Slonimsky's *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns*.

Thesaurus scale 252

Random generation

Figure 8: Two-scale interpolation example: between the *Thesaurus*' 252nd scale and a random generation.

exploring random melodic patterns, as it offers many scales to pick and explore from. As mentioned on the previous interpolation examples, the creative qualities of the generations can be seen clearly, combining the different scales of the latent space and applying their insertional techniques to create something novel yet structured.

Figure 9: Two-scale interpolation example: between two randomly generated scales.

5.3 Four-Scale Interpolation Experiments

The four-scale interpolation feature is a very similar concept to the two-scale interpolation, as it lets the generation of a 2-dimensional grid that represents the latent space (16 dimensions) in a 2D space. To run a four-scale interpolation, four scales, either randomly generated or from the thesaurus, need to be positioned on each corner of a grid, and the rest of the empty spaces will be filled out by scales that make a smooth transition from one point to another in any direction.

The resulting averaged metrics for 500 four-scale interpolations using LERP were:

- Structure Similarity Index Measure (SSIM): 0.8853
- LBP Euclidean Distance (LBPED): 6.4684

These values imply that the average grid interpolation ran by our model has good transitions between scales, making a smooth 2D representation of our VAE’s latent space. It is important to notice the slightly lower performance for this interpolation type, when compared to two-scale interpolations, which could be justified by the lower amount of steps between scales.

5.3.1 Four-Scale Interpolation Example

The results will be shown in small groups, making sure the functionality of this aspect of our model is correctly demonstrated, while also not taking too much space, as each grid includes 25 scales.

The chosen example includes the following scales in their said positions as shown in figure 10, having two scales belonging to our dataset (scales 196 and 317), and two random generations for the four corners of our grid.

Figure 12: 2D Interpolation example: Diagonal 2.

The results highlight the potential of VAEs to produce musically coherent and innovative scales; however, several limitations should be addressed. The training was limited to a subset of the thesaurus, with fixed-length scales of 37 notes. Future research could evaluate the model’s performance on other datasets, including polyphonic music or scales from alternative theoretical frameworks, to determine its broader applicability. Additionally, while metrics such as sparseness, coverage, and symmetry offer insights into the properties of the generated scales, they primarily provide qualitative assessments. Incorporating listener-based evaluations or advanced computational metrics could yield a more comprehensive understanding of the generated scales’ musical relevance.

The interpolation experiments, while demonstrating smooth transitions within the latent space, were constrained to fixed bounds, with no exploration of extrapolation beyond these limits. Such experiments could provide additional insights into the robustness and flexibility of the model. Furthermore, while selected examples illustrate the creative potential of the model, a more systematic and quantitative approach to evaluating the generated data would allow for comparisons with other generative techniques, enhancing the study’s reproducibility and rigor.

Finally, this research opens up the possibility of using models trained on Slonimsky’s thesaurus as foundational tools for transfer learning. Exploring how pre-trained models could be fine-tuned with other datasets or styles may further expand their application to diverse musical contexts.

7 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of variational autoencoders in generating and interpolating musical scales derived from Slonimsky’s Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns. By training on a symbolic dataset and leveraging robust generative techniques, the model produced musically coherent scales while enabling smooth transitions between known and generated scales. These results suggest that such models can be valuable tools for assisting composers in exploring new musical ideas. Future work should address current limitations by expanding datasets, incorporating more comprehensive evaluation metrics, and investigating the model’s behavior in extrapolated regions of the latent space. These developments could further enhance the applicability of AI-based systems in music composition and creativity.

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